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THE STUDY OF THE SEDENTARY STATE OF MEDICAL UNIVERSITY STUDENTS ABOUT BREAST CANCER AND METHODS OF RADIATION DIAGNOSIS OF ITS PATHOLOGY

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Annotation: In the course of the study, an analysis of mortality from breast cancer in the Republic of Belarus was carried out. When analyzing mortality by regions and Minsk, the highest indicator in 2019 is observed in residents of the Vitebsk region (13.5 per 100 thousand population), Minsk (14.0 per 100 thousand population), Gomel region (14.6 per 100 thousand population). However, in 2019, the mortality rate from breast cancer decreased in the Minsk region by 1.13 times (11.2 per 100 thousand population) compared to the previous period. In other areas, there is an increase in the mortality rate from this pathology. The level of awareness of Grodno State Medical University students about the risks of development, methods of diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer was revealed. Based on the results of an anonymous survey, it was found that girls have a low level of awareness on the topic of breast pathologies.

Keywords: breast, breast cancer, mortality, awareness, students

ИЗУЧЕНИЕ ОСВЕДОМЛЕННОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ МЕДИЦНСКОГО УНИВЕРСИТЕТА О РАКЕ МОЛОЧНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ И МЕТОДАХ ЛУЧЕВОЙ ДИАГНОСТИКИ ДАННОЙ ПАТОЛОГИИ

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Аннотация: В процессе исследования проведен анализ смертности от рака молочной железы в Республике Беларусь. При анализе смертности по областям и г. Минску наиболее высокий показатель в 2019 гг. наблюдается у жителей Витебской области (13,5 на 100 тысяч населения), г. Минска (14,0 на 100 тысяч населения), Гомельской области (14,6 на 100 тысяч населения). Однако, за 2019 г. показатель смертности от рака молочной железы уменьшился в Минской области в 1,13 раза (11,2 на 100 тысяч населения) по сравнению с предыдущим периодом. В других областях отмечается увеличение показателя смертности от данной патологии. Выявлен уровень осведомленности студентов Гродненского государственного медицинского университета о рисках развития, способах диагностики и методах лечения рака молочной железы. Исходя из результатов анонимного опроса установлено, что девушки имеют низкий уровень информированности по теме патологий молочных желез.

Ключевые слова: молочная железа, рак молочной железы, смертность, осведомленность, студенты

Relevance. Diseases of the mammary glands are one of the urgent problems of modern radiation diagnostics. In most countries of the world, breast cancer ranks first in the structure of cancer incidence in women. In the Republic of Belarus, breast cancer ranks second (17.6 %) [1, 7].

In 2020, 2.3 million women were diagnosed with breast cancer, while 685,000 deaths from this disease were registered worldwide. According to data at the end of 2020, 7.8 million women were still alive who had been diagnosed with breast cancer over the past five years, which means that this type of cancer is the most common cancer in the world [2, 8].

The goal of the WHO Global Initiative to Fight Breast Cancer is to reduce mortality from this disease in the world by 2.5 % annually, which will prevent 2.5 million deaths from breast cancer worldwide between 2020 and 2040. Reducing mortality from breast cancer in the world by 2.5 % per year will prevent 25 % of deaths from this type of cancer by 2030 and 40 % of cases by 2040 among women under the age of 70. The three main components necessary to achieve these goals are: health promotion measures that promote early detection of the disease; timely diagnosis; comprehensive treatment of breast cancer [3].

There are the following types of breast tumor diagnosis: radiological – mammography, ductography (galactography), pneumocystography; ultrasonic; magnetic resonance imaging (MR mammography).

X-ray mammography is the leading and widespread, in some cases the only method of diagnosing these neoplasms, for example, a variant of the

preclinical form of cancer. According to the recommendations of the American Cancer Society, it is recommended to perform the first mammography at 35-39 years old, repeat it at the age of 40-49 years with an interval of 1-2 years, and after 50 years to conduct mammography annually [4, 6]. This diagnostic method has a number of advantages: detection of ductal formations and the possibility of detecting microcalcines in the absence of a solid component, while the sensitivity of the method ranges from 46.2 to 76.9 %.

Ultrasound examination. Ultrasound, in turn, has certain limitations due to the limits of its capabilities, such as: low informativeness in fat involution, inexpediency of use for breast cancer screening (a high percentage of false negative conclusions, lack of visualization of non-palpable cancer in the form of a cluster of microcalcines – due to the physical characteristics of the method) [5].

Magnetic resonance imaging (MR mammography) of the mammary glands is a new opportunity for non-invasive examination of the mammary glands without surgery, and most importantly, without X-rays. Due to the high contrast of various breast tissues, MRI allows you to study their structure in detail and identify the presence of pathological processes [6]. Compared with X-ray mammography and ultrasound diagnostics, magnetic resonance imaging has a number of significant advantages, and the informative value of the method does not depend on the following factors: breast tissue density; the severity of fibrocystic mastopathy; the presence of postoperative scars; post-radiation fibrosis.

Purpose. To study the most common methods of diagnosis and treatment of breast cancer. To identify the level of awareness of Grodno State Medical University students about the risks of development, methods of breast cancer diagnosis.

Materials and methods of a research. The study was conducted using an anonymous survey, which took place on the basis of the Grodno State Medical University. It was attended by 150 female respondents of the pediatric, medical and diagnostic faculty aged 18 to 23 years. The achievement of the goal set in the work was carried out using comparative analytical and evaluation methods. The main criterion for inclusion: informed consent. The results were processed using nonparametric statistics methods using the Statistica 6.0 analysis package and Excel.

Results and discussion. When studying the awareness of students about the main methods of breast cancer diagnosis, it was revealed that the smallest number of respondents believe that the most informative study in the diagnosis of breast cancer is magnetic resonance imaging 50 %, while 35 % of girls voted for the ultrasound method, the remaining 15 % voted for X-ray mammography. The best way to diagnose breast cancer, based on an anonymous survey, was the method of X-ray mammography. It was revealed that only 60 % of students conduct an independent examination of the mammary glands, visiting a

gynecologist: 50 % – 1 time a year, 15 % twice a year. While the remaining 35 % of female students do not undergo self-diagnosis due to lack of awareness of this problem. It was found that 30 % of students believe that this pathology is caused by excessive stress, while 60 % voted for the option of drinking a large amount of alcohol; the remaining 10 % voted that this pathology occurs due to hereditary predisposition. The results of an anonymous survey of girls showed that girls have a low level of awareness on the topic of breast pathologies.

Conclusions. Breast cancer is one of the leading causes of death in women with cancer. When analyzing mortality from this oncological pathology by regions and Minsk, the highest indicator in 2019 was observed in residents of the Vitebsk region (13.5 per 100 thousand population), Minsk (14.0 per 100 thousand population), Gomel region (14.6 per 100 thousand population). However, in 2019, the mortality rate from breast cancer decreased in the Minsk region by 1.13 times (11.2 per 100 thousand population). In other areas, there is an increase in the mortality rate from this pathology. Therefore, it is very important to carry out early diagnosis of breast cancer in a timely manner. Today, mammography is the leading method of breast cancer screening. High-quality mammographic screening ultimately leads to a significant (up to 30 %) reduction in mortality from breast cancer. Women who, for various reasons, do not participate in mammographic screening should be informed that there are no other methods of examination that could equally effectively reduce mortality from this disease.

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